

CORRUPTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION – VIEWS AND EXPERIENCES OF STUDENTS FROM THE FACULTY OF SECURITY – SKOPJE

Katerina Krstevska Savovska

Faculty of Security – Skopje
katerina.krstevska@uklo.edu.mk

Elena Dimovska

Faculty of Security – Skopje
elena.dimovska@uklo.edu.mk

Abstract

Corruption in higher education poses a significant threat to academic integrity and quality of education. It can take many forms, including bribery for passing exams, nepotism, sexual extortion, and the sale of academic materials. Such practices not only erode trust in the education system, but also have the potential to destroy the ideals of a young student and affect the person they will become after completing the studies.

The primary goal of this study is to conduct an initial research among students across all three cycles of study at the Faculty of Security – Skopje, which will later be expanded to include students from the entire University “St. Kliment Ohridski” – Bitola. Thus, this paper examines the issue of corruption in higher education based on a survey conducted among students at the Faculty of Security – Skopje. The research uses the definition of corruption as outlined in the Rulebook about the work and remuneration of the authorized person for receiving corruption reports at the University “St. Kliment Ohridski” – Bitola.

This study assesses students’ knowledge, attitudes, and personal experiences related to corruption in the academic environment. The anonymous questionnaire explores students’ perceptions of the impact of corruption and identifies the most common corrupt practices they encounter. Furthermore, the study explores whether students have witnessed or experienced corruption, their willingness to report such incidents, and their awareness of reporting mechanisms. Finally, the paper gathers student suggestions for effective measures to reduce corruption in higher education.

This research provides a comprehensive overview of the challenges and perceptions surrounding academic corruption, offering valuable insights for future policy development and institutional reforms.

Key words: *corruption, higher education, students*

INTRODUCTION

Corruption in higher education undermines the very foundation of academic integrity and the credibility of educational institutions. It distorts merit-based evaluation, fosters inequality, and weakens students' trust in the system designed to nurture ethical and competent professionals. In contexts where education is considered both a public good and a pathway to professional success, corruption becomes a particularly dangerous phenomenon, as it affects not only institutional reputation but also the formation of social and moral values among future professionals.

Corruption in higher education is a pervasive global challenge, with evidence demonstrating that it affects institutions across all regions to varying degrees (Glendinning, Orim, & King, 2019). This issue manifests in diverse forms, including political interference, nepotism, fraudulent academic credentials, bribery, and academic dishonesty. The scope and impact of corruption undermine the integrity, quality, and accessibility of higher education worldwide. North Macedonia is no exception to these challenges. Recognizing the global and local prevalence of corruption highlights the urgent need for comprehensive strategies to promote transparency, accountability, and integrity in higher education institutions.

This study focuses on the perceptions, attitudes, and personal experiences of students from the Faculty of Security – Skopje regarding corruption in higher education. The research was conducted through an anonymous online survey distributed via Google Forms to students from all three cycles of studies at the faculty. The purpose of the study was to obtain an initial insight into how students perceive corruption in their academic environment, their awareness of reporting mechanisms, and their suggestions for effective anti-corruption measures.

At the beginning of the survey, respondents were provided with a clear and context-specific definition of corruption, consistent with the Rulebook on the work and remuneration of the authorized person for receiving reports of corruption at the University "St. Kliment Ohridski" - Bitola (University "St. Kliment Ohridski" – Bitola, 2020). According to this Rulebook: "Corruption refers to the intentional actions of an official who, directly or through an intermediary, requests, receives, or accepts a promise of any benefit for themselves or for a third party, in order to act or refrain from acting in line with their duties, or to exercise their responsibilities contrary to official obligations. It also refers to intentional actions by a person who, directly or through an intermediary, promises or provides any benefit to an official, for themselves or for a third party, with the aim of influencing the official to act or refrain from acting in line with their duties, or to exercise their responsibilities contrary to official obligations."

Despite the relevance of the topic and the institutional support for conducting the research, the response rate was relatively low — only 95 students out of 1,207 participated. The reasons for such **limited engagement** remain uncertain, though several possible explanations exist. One possibility is **survey fatigue**, as students may have been oversaturated with online questionnaires following years of increased digital communication. Another factor may be **timing**, since the survey was distributed during the examination period, when students are less inclined to engage in additional academic activities. Finally, the **sensitivity of the topic** itself could have discouraged participation, as corruption remains a subject that many perceive as risky to discuss openly, even under conditions of anonymity.

Nevertheless, the collected data provide valuable insights into students' perceptions and the broader institutional climate. They reveal not only the extent of awareness and distrust in formal mechanisms but also the willingness of students to propose constructive measures for change. The findings thus serve as an initial but significant step toward understanding and addressing corruption within academic institutions, offering directions for both further research and practical reform.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The sixteen questions of the survey were divided into four sections: 1. "Demographic data" (two questions), 2. "Assessment of students' views" (five questions), 3. "Personal experiences" (five questions), and 4. "Awareness and recommendations" (4 questions). And as mentioned before, the survey was submitted to 1207 students of the Faculty of Security – Skopje. However, their response was very low; i.e. only 7.9% (95 students) filled out the questionnaire, out of which 61.1% were female and 38.9% were male.

Chart No. 1 Gender of the students who filled out the questionnaire

Since the Faculty of Security – Skopje organizes lectures on three cycles of studies (first, second and third), the survey was submitted to students that are / have been studying in the years 2020 – 2024. Or to be more precise, the survey was delivered to:

- 1055 students of the first cycle of studies,
- 112 students of the second cycle of studies, and
- 40 students of the third cycle of studies.

Apart from gender, Section 1 ('Demographic data') collected information on the students' cycle of studies. The 95 collected responses show that the highest response rate is among students enrolled on the first cycle of studies. In essence, 64.2% of the students are enrolled on the first cycle of studies (18.9% are attending first year, 25.3% are attending second year, 10.5% are attending third year and 9.5% are attending fourth year), 21.5% on the second cycle of studies and only 14.7% on the third cycle of studies. This distribution is also due to the fact that most of the students that are enrolled at the Faculty of Security – Skopje and to whom the questionnaire was sent are the first-cycle students.

Chart No. 2 The enrolled cycle of studies

In connection with the research topic, by the first question of Section 2. “Assessment of students’ views” the students were asked to give their opinion on whether corruption in higher education affects the quality of studies in the Republic of Macedonia, and at the same time four answers were offered to them (Does not affect at all; Partially does not affect; Partially affects; Affects a lot). From their choices, it can be concluded that students believe that corruption has an impact on the quality of studies because 97.6% of them chose the two offered options “Partially affects” (72.6%) and “Affects a lot” (25.3%). On the other hand, only 2.1% chose the option “Partially does not affect” and none of them chose the option “Does not affect at all”.

Chart No. 3 Students’ perception of the impact of corruption on the quality of the studies

Next, the students were asked to rate the level of corruption in the higher education in the Republic of Macedonia from 1 to 5, with a note that “1” means that there is no corruption and “5” means that there is a lot of corruption. Most students rated the level of corruption in higher education with 4 (40%), followed by 3 (29.5%), 5 (21.1%), 2 (8.4%) and 1 (1%). This is truly worrying, as 90.6% of students gave corruption a “passing” rating (from 3 and up).

Chart No. 4 Students' perception of the level of corruption in higher education in the Republic of Macedonia

As a follow-up to the previous question, students were asked once again to rate the level of corruption, but now within their own faculty. Contrary to the above, most of the students chose the option 1 or “no corruption” (34.7%), followed by option 2 (27.4%). The other students, or 37.9%, have chosen option 3 (22.1%), 4 (10.5%) and 5 (5.3%). This implies that the level of corruption within the Faculty of Security – Skopje, based on the opinion of its students, does not follow the trend of the level of corruption in the higher education as a whole, but on the contrary - the level of corruption within the Faculty of Security – Skopje received a negative rating or a rating of 1 (“no corruption”), and such rating is commendable.

Chart No. 5 Students' perception of the level of corruption at the Faculty of Security – Skopje

When asked about the forms of corrupt behaviour that, in their opinion, most often occur within higher education, students were allowed to select multiple answers. A considerable proportion of respondents, i.e. 74.7%, perceive that the most common form is when professors pressure students to purchase their books in order to pass an exam or obtain a higher grade. The second most frequently perceived form, selected by 54.7% of

respondents, is giving money to a professor to pass an exam or achieve a higher grade, followed by giving gifts for the same purpose (40%). Furthermore, 17.9% of students believed that professors sometimes pressure students into intimate relationships in exchange for passing or receiving a higher grade. It is important to emphasize that none of the respondents believe that students are favoured because of family, friendship or other personal ties with professors.

Since the last provided option or “Other” was chosen by 9.5% of the students, they were asked to provide an answer why they did so, i.e. to point out to other behaviours that have not been listed in the options provided above. The answers that they gave are the following: using a political and other business connections to acquire inappropriate degrees and obtain positions/titles in higher education that are not deserved and have been acquired in a corrupt manner, e.g. assistant, associate professor, full professor, etc. at the expense of degrees obtained from prestigious international or domestic faculties that are not properly valued and evaluated; urging through a friend who is close to the professor or through a professor who is close to the professor with whom the student is supposed to take the exam; certain services in return; “giving money to buy a degree, but not at my faculty - this happens more often at private faculties”; family ties, children or relatives of professors at the faculty; seeking connections through mutual friends, and one of them responded with “No”.

Chart No. 6 Students’ perception of forms of corrupt behaviour that most often occur within higher education

The first question of Section 3. “Personal experiences”, was about whether the students have ever witnessed or have been a victim of corrupt practices at the Faculty of Security – Skopje, and 81.1% answered “No”.

Chart No. 7 Students' experience of witnessing or being victims of corruption at the Faculty of Security – Skopje

The others chose “Yes” (18.9%) and pointed out several situations, such as obligation to buy textbooks (through “book package” or from the professors themselves – not to have a possibility to use scripts or previously used books in order to save money, as well as the “book package” is a must in order to obtain an index; to buy a textbook in order to take an exam; to be forced by the professor to buy a book in order to take an exam; anticipating insufficient knowledge, based on the fact that he/she did not buy a book, which he/she thinks that is inadequate for the level of knowledge required for the study cycle; not buying the book had cost him/her a lower grade; without buying the book, it was not possible to get a grade on an exam that he/she had already passed; professor takes money from the student; not choosing the best candidate for a job position “assistant” who had 10 as an average of grades, had a master's degree from a prestigious international faculty, as well as had an evidently far better CV; to be a witness when an urging happened in order for a student to pass the test; being a witness to a request on intimate relations. From the given responses, it can be concluded that students evaluate as a negative behaviour, i.e. a corrupt practice, when they are being forced to buy books (from a professor or through a “book package”).

Having identified the behaviours that students perceive as corrupt within higher education, it is equally important to explore their reactions when encountering such practices. The following findings focus on students' willingness, or lack thereof, to report corruption.

Chart No. 8 Display of the percentage of reported corruption cases

The findings of our study reveal that 82.5% of students who faced some form of corrupt behaviour in higher education chose not to report it. For comparison, this tendency of non-reporting by students is confirmed by the discussion held by the Institute for Democracy during the event “Forms of Corruption in Higher Education”, which concluded that although students are aware of corruption within academia, they rarely take steps to report it (Institute for Democracy, 2023). This alignment points to a significant gap between the recognition of corrupt practices and the willingness to act on them, driven by factors such as mistrust in institutions, fear of negative consequences, and feelings of helplessness. These insights underscore the urgent need to establish trust-enhancing, accessible, and protective reporting mechanisms to empower students in combating corruption effectively.

Students who indicated that they chose not to report the incident were subsequently asked to identify the primary reasons behind their decision. The summarized results are presented below.

Chart No. 9 Main reasons for not reporting corruption cases

Distrust and scepticism are the biggest obstacles – more than three quarters (78.2%) of students do not report due to distrust in the institutions and lack of belief that there will be a result. Fear is less prevalent, but still a significant factor (12.5%). The information aspect (not knowing where to report) is not a problem, which may indicate that the mechanisms are known, but are not considered efficient. No respondents indicated threats as a reason for not reporting.

Despite no indication of threats or lack of knowledge of where to report, it is important to highlight that when asked about familiarity with the corruption reporting mechanisms at the faculty, 46.3% of respondents stated they were not aware of them, while the remainder confirmed their knowledge. This suggests a significant portion still lack awareness of internal procedures.

Chart No. 10 Familiarity with the mechanisms for reporting corruption at the faculty

The apparent inconsistency between these two survey findings where students initially do not identify lack of knowledge as a key obstacle, yet nearly half later report not knowing where and how to report corruption, can be interpreted through several complementary factors. First, the framing of the questions likely influenced the responses: when asked about reasons for not reporting, students focused on attitudinal barriers such as distrust and scepticism, while the second question specifically prompted reflection on procedural awareness. This indicates that many students may have only a general sense that reporting mechanisms exist, without concrete knowledge of how to access them. Furthermore, the prevailing distrust in institutional responsiveness may diminish the perceived relevance of such knowledge, as students who doubt the effectiveness of reporting channels may not consider them a viable option regardless of awareness. Together, these findings reveal both a perceptual and institutional gap that hinders effective anti-corruption engagement within the academic setting.

Respondents were also asked to indicate which method of reporting corruption in higher education they consider to be the most acceptable, and the results are provided below.

Chart No. 11 The most favourable mechanisms for reporting corruption according to students

Students show the highest level of trust in the authorized person, indicating a preference for a formal and independent reporting mechanism, which underscores the need for institutions to actively promote and strengthen this channel. Faculty leadership, primarily the dean, is the second most trusted option, reflecting some student confidence but more in administrative or managerial roles rather than independent ones. The student ombudsman plays a notable yet smaller role, suggesting potential for further development as an intermediary. Only two students selected "Other", with one stating corruption reports should go to the police and Public Prosecutor’s Office, and the other recommending reporting to the dean in the presence of faculty staff. This demonstrates that although there are diverse opinions, most answers aligned with the survey’s predefined options rather than original suggestions.

Finally, students were asked, in an open-ended question, what they thought should be done to reduce corruption in higher education. A wide range of responses were received, and for the sake of clarity, they were grouped into six larger clusters.

Cluster analysis

➤ **Financial incentives and material status**

- Increase in professors' salaries.
- State support and better standards for teaching staff.
- Reduce the possibility of corruption through higher salaries and professional conditions.

Students suggest that improving professors' salaries and professional conditions can reduce corruption by decreasing financial motives. This cluster reflects the belief that economic stability for staff diminishes the temptation to engage in corrupt acts. Higher salaries raise the "cost" of unethical conduct, making corruption less economically rational for individuals (Klitgaard, 2011).

➤ **Transparency, digitalization and modernization**

- Introducing fully digitalized and anonymized processes (taking exams through platforms with hidden identities).
- Introducing a database of questions, public assessment.

This cluster highlights the importance of using technology to make processes objective and less prone to manipulation, such as anonymized digital exams and public databases. It addresses structural vulnerabilities by limiting opportunities for corrupt behaviour.

➤ **Control, supervision and sanctions**

- Independent inspection bodies for control of faculties.
- Constant checks of professors and exams.
- Introduction of rapid disciplinary procedures.
- Strict penalties and public announcement of corrupt individuals

The call for independent inspections, swift disciplinary action, and strict penalties aligns with deterrence theory, which posits that crime (in our case corruption) decreases when the expected cost of punishment outweighs the benefits (Onwudiwe, Odo, & Onyeozili, n.d., Johnson, 2019). Visible enforcement and public exposure serve to increase perceived risks, thus deterring corrupt behaviour.

➤ **Reporting and protection of whistleblowers**

- Introducing persons/authorized bodies for reporting.
- Anonymous mechanisms and protection of students who report.
- Encouraging students to actively report.
- Involving the student ombudsman and independent bodies.

The emphasis here is on creating safe, anonymous channels for reporting corruption and protecting those who come forward. Involving independent bodies and the student ombudsman reflects recognition of the critical role of trusted intermediaries in anti-corruption efforts.

➤ **Ethical culture and awareness**

- Raising public and academic awareness.
- Organizing public forums and discussions.
- Promoting integrity and ethical values.
- Creating a culture of merit and valuing knowledge

Students call for raising awareness and actively promoting academic integrity and ethical behaviour. This cluster targets the root cultural causes of corruption by advocating for a shift in values toward meritocracy and honesty.

➤ **Reforming the education system and staff**

- Replacing corrupt professors.
- Better staff selection and strict criteria for teachers.
- Control over professor-student relations.
- Reducing the role of private faculties or closing them.

Replacing corrupt staff and enforcing strict hiring criteria seek to ensure integrity at the personnel level. Control over professor-student relations and scrutiny of private faculties focus on systemic reforms that prevent abuse of power and commercialized education models prone to corruption.

The diversity of clusters shows that students recognize corruption as a multifaceted problem requiring solutions beyond mere punishment. They emphasize prevention through transparency, adequate financial incentives, ethical culture, and institutional reform. The balance between procedural mechanisms (digitalization, reporting) and cultural shifts (ethics, awareness) highlights a mature understanding of the complexity of corruption control in academia.

CONCLUSION

Distrust in institutions is the biggest barrier to fighting corruption, as most students believe reporting will not lead to change. Students demand systemic and structural solutions: independent oversight, digitalization, and transparent procedures that minimize personal influence. Corruption is seen as stemming from both material causes (low professor salaries, weak conditions) and cultural/systemic factors (nepotism, lack of meritocracy).

The most realistic and supported measures are a mix of preventive and repressive actions: promoting ethics and awareness while also applying strict sanctions and institutional supervision. Radical ideas (closing private faculties, replacing all staff) exist, but most students focus on practical reforms such as transparency, reporting mechanisms, and modernization.

The main limitation of the study is the small sample size, which does not allow generalization. With only 95 respondents out of a total of 1,209 students, the results should be interpreted cautiously. The limited participation may reflect methodological or contextual constraints, such as low motivation to engage in online surveys, exam-period timing, or reluctance to address sensitive topics related to institutional integrity. Nevertheless, this limitation underscores the importance of conducting broader, longitudinal, and comparative studies across different faculties and universities to obtain more robust and generalizable data.

Despite its constraints, this research provides an important initial step toward understanding how students perceive corruption within academia and how these perceptions shape their trust, engagement, and moral outlook. The results underline the urgent need for higher education institutions to strengthen transparency, accountability, and communication with students. Building trust is not merely a procedural goal but a moral imperative, one essential for restoring integrity and ensuring that universities remain spaces of fairness, knowledge, and ethical growth.

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